

1 **Xist transgenic culture systems and Xist+ human pluripotent stem cells reveal transcriptional**
2 **targets of Xist.**

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7 We identify here through the study of total transcription in human cells engineered to express an Xist
8 transgene, and in human pluripotent stem cells selected at the clonal level for Xist positivity (Xist+ hES),
9 and proteomic study of Xist interacting proteins a network of epigenetic molecules whose expression is
10 controlled by Xist. The range of epigenetic molecules controlled by Xist included members of the plant
11 homeodomain *Phf*, chromobox *Cbx*, methyl-CpG binding *Mbd*, bromodomain *Brd*, chromodomain *Chd* and
12 histone lysine demethylase *Kdm* families. Xist could repress or activate most of its targets consistent with
13 an imprinting function that could both silence or derepress targets. *Phf6* was a transcriptional target of
14 Xist and an Xist-interacting protein, as were *Cbx5* and *Cbx3*, as well as *Kdm5d*. The network identified
15 here represents a cell-type specific group of molecules with as of yet largely unidentified function in Xist
16 transcriptional regulation.
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